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Cell wall glucose analysis of AIR fraction of rosette leaves from *exo70B* mutants in comparison to WT

Supplementary Figure 1. A) Plot shows steady-state (400 ppm) stomatal conductance level of WT and mutants including second mutant version *exo70B2* Salk line and *exo70B1/tn2* double mutant. One-way ANOVA with post-hoc Tukey HSD was used for statistics, $p < 0.05$, $n > 5$ independent leaves per genotype, error bars represent SD. B) Cell wall analysis of mock and chitosan treated *exo70B* mutants in comparison to WT. Cell wall glucose amounts in *exo70B* mutants' cell walls are at the similar level as in WT plants; $n = 8-9$; two-way ANOVA $p < 0.05$.